

Social Media Platforms Required for Marketing Education Graduates for Sales of Products and Services as Perceived by Business Educators in Higher Institutions in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The study assessed social media platforms required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa state. The objectives of the study were to assess social media platforms such as YouTube, WhatsApp and Facebook required for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa state. Three research questions and three hypotheses were stated and tested. Descriptive survey research design was used to carry out this study and 39 male and female business educators in three (3) in higher institutions in Bayelsa state was used as population for the study. No sampling was done due to the small size of the population; 39 copies filled by male and female business educators were used for the study. The instrument for the data collected was a structured questionnaire containing 30 items. The statistical method used for data analysis was mean and standard deviation while the t-test was used as a parametric technique in testing the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that YouTube, WhatsApp and Facebook are required for sales of products and services as perceived by male and female business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa state. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that social media platforms like YouTube, WhatsApp and Facebook are required for sales of products and services as perceived by male and female business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa. It was recommended among others that Students and marketing education graduates should take the initiative in learning and mastering popular social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, WhatsApp, and emerging platforms like TikTok.

Keywords: social media platforms, required, marketing education, products, services, sales, graduates, business education.

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving digital landscape, social media platforms has emerged as a pivotal tool for marketing, revolutionizing the way businesses engage with customers and promote their products and services. This transformation necessitates that marketing education graduates are well-versed in utilizing various social media platforms to thrive in the competitive business environment. Recognizing this need, educational institutions, particularly universities, play a crucial role in equipping students with the necessary skills and knowledge. The emergence of social media

platforms in today's technology-driven 21st century cannot be overstated. Businesses and marketing organizations have experienced significant boosts in sales of their products and services through these platforms and their associated handles. It is no surprise that most businesses now have social media accounts across multiple platforms. With the rise of social media, businesses have shifted away from traditional methods such as TV jingles, face-to-face advertising, word-of-mouth, and newspaper publications. Social media platforms has transformed and altered the marketing environment (Saboo, Kumar, and Ramani, 2015).

The rise of social platforms has placed a strong emphasis on the importance of graduates, especially those with a marketing education graduates background, to possess knowledge and skills in navigating various social media platforms. This is because employers now require prospective applicants to have social media handles and presence in order to fill various positions. According to Okoro (2020), the focus of product and service advertisements has largely shifted to social media platforms, and employers are leveraging these platforms to their advantage. The growth and development of information and communication technology have contributed to the increasing prominence of social media platforms in the corporate business world. Social media platforms serve as interactive spaces for individuals and organizations to engage through text, audio, videos, and pictures. The platforms used in this study include YouTube, WhatsApp and Facebook.

YouTube is a platform marketing education graduates can use to increase sales of products and services. YouTube is an audio-visual platform that allows marketing education graduates to create, view and post videos, including marketing content such as TV clips, movie clips, music videos, and promotional videos. It enables marketing education graduates to create channels, share contents, and connect with clients worldwide. According to ComScore (2012), YouTube ranks as the top video internet viewing site, with over 800 million users watching more than 4 billion hours of video each month. Yusuf (2023) revealed that YouTube plays a crucial role in the expansion of businesses because it offers a valuable platform for companies to promote their products and services, engage with customers, and expand their market reach. Rich (2018) claimed that YouTube enables businesses to provide goods or services, market their products, discover new offerings, and improve existing ones through promotional activities. Marketing education graduates can search for skill-related videos to improve employability and practical skills, and learn more about companies of interest, sharing these videos via WhatsApp statuses.

WhatsApp is a valuable tool for marketing education graduates to market products and services. Known for instant messaging, WhatsApp has surpassed traditional SMS due to its ability to exchange large volumes of messages and media files (Church & de Oliveira, 2013). Bansal and Joshi (2014) reported that WhatsApp creates a very positive impact on regular users. Marketing education graduates can send products and services through audio, images, video, and text messages. WhatsApp supports individual and group chats, video, and voice calls using internet/Wi-Fi or data. Lin (2020) opined WhatsApp advertising has emerged as a prominent trend among social media platforms, with WhatsApp status, private messages, broadcast messages, and

WhatsApp chat groups being inundated with images and videos showcasing various products and services. Marketing education graduates can use WhatsApp to share contents on products and services to increase sales, gather relevant information on market trend, create job-related groups, and add employers, gaining insights into required skills and connecting via Facebook and other platforms.

Facebook is another popular social media platform that offers extensive interpersonal communication capabilities, emphasizing mobility and interaction (Paxson, 2010). Arteaga, Cortijo and Javed (2014) found that Facebook adoption positively affects users' purposes for using it. Marketing education graduates can utilize Facebook for messaging, news feeds, timelines, groups, photos, pages, subscriptions, and video calling. The timeline feature allows customization of the Facebook page, while the news feed presents updates from one's network. Marketing education graduates can post products and services via text, pictures, messages, links, blogs, and videos on their and others' timelines, connect with friends, and explore clients, products and companies of interest on Facebook.

A product is a physical object that is made available for purchase, consideration, or use. Products are physical objects that can be touched or held. A product is something that can be provided to fulfil a need or desire. More specifically, a product can be classified as an item, service, action, individual, location, establishment, or concept. Product according to Kotler (2012), is anything that can be presented to a market for consideration, purchase, use, or consumption to fulfil a need or desire. Berry et al. (2012) also emphasize that the notion of a product extends beyond tangible items, encompassing anything that can satisfy a need or want, such as individuals, locations, businesses, events, services and concepts. Services refer to distinct, intangible activities that fulfil the desires of customers. These intangible tasks cater to the needs of customers and industrial users when effectively developed, priced, promoted, and delivered to the targeted market segment. A service possesses the attributes of intangibility, inseparability, challenges in standardization, perishability, and indispensability. A service is defined as an activity or task that one individual offers to another, typically intangible and not involving ownership. Oftentimes, services are both produced and utilized at the same time (Berry, et al 2012)

The digital revolution of social media platforms such as YouTube, WhatsApp and Facebook have increased products and services sales. Each platform offers unique features and benefits, catering to different marketing needs and consumer behaviours. Marketing education graduates should possess skills to navigate these platforms required in today's market. Hence this study.

Statement of the problem

Social media platforms as key components of communication technologies, have recently transformed the way job requirements are handled in contemporary business organizations, particularly in the realm of digital marketing. The utilization of platforms such as YouTube, WhatsApp, Facebook and others has left many graduates lacking the necessary skills in social media marketing unemployed in the job market. This has led to a rise in societal issues, including

nuisance, armed robbery, and unrest, as these unemployed graduates struggle to meet the high demands of businesses and organizations. This shift in technology emphasizes the importance of adequately preparing marketing students in school to adapt to the ever-evolving landscape of social media platforms, ensuring their relevance and competitiveness in today's business environment.

Theoretical framework

This paper anchored on the Uses and Gratifications Theory, Diffusion of Innovation Theory and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM):

Uses and Gratifications Theory

Elihu Katz, Jay Blumler, and Michael Gurevitch introduced the Uses and Gratification Theory in 1974. This theory focuses on the value that media holds for audiences and users. Individuals can utilize social media to alleviate tensions, address conflicts, and bring attention to social issues. The study of the uses and gratification theory delves into the motivations and needs that prompt individuals to engage with social media platforms. It investigates how users seek gratification, whether it be through entertainment, information, social interaction, or self-expression, in their online endeavours.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory:

E.M. Rogers developed the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory in 1962. This theory examines how new ideas, technologies, or behaviours are adopted and spread within social media platforms. It delves into the various factors that impact the speed and scope of adoption, as well as the patterns of diffusion among different user groups

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The utilization of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), proposed by Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw (1989) also served as the foundation for this study. TAM was employed as a means to elucidate and forecast the acceptance of technology within an information system by its end users. Extensive evidence has demonstrated TAM's efficacy in modelling technology acceptance and usage among various entities such as firms, organizations, and individuals. The fundamental TAM framework relied on two crucial factors, namely perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, to anticipate user intention and usage. The adoption and use of social media platforms by most marketing businesses is to improve sales of products and services performance.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to assess social media platforms required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa state.

Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

2. WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.
3. Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. Is YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State?
2. Is WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State?
3. Is Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Methodology

The research adopted descriptive survey research design. The population comprised business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State. It comprises of 11 business educators from Federal university Otuoke , 8 from Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island Bayelsa State and 20 from Isaac Jasper Boro, College of Education, Sagbama, Bayelsa State; totalling 39 respondent (23 male and 16 female). Due to the manageable size of the population, a census approach was employed. A self-design questionnaire titled "Social Media Platforms required for Marketing Education Graduates for Sales of Products and Services as perceived by Business Educators in Higher Institutions Questionnaire" (SMPMEGSPSBEHIQ) consisting of 30 items served as the research instrument. The questionnaire was structured according to the research questions in

conjunction with the research objectives. The responses were optioned on a 4 point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA), 4 points; Agree (A), 3 point; Disagree (D), 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD), 1 point. Face, content, and construct validity of the instrument were established through validation by three experts, including business educator and two test evaluators from Federal University Otuoke. Corrections and additions suggested by these experts were incorporated into the final draft of the SMPMEGSPSBEHIQ. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined using the Cronbach alpha technique, resulting in an overall coefficient of 0.85, indicating good reliability. 39 copies of the questionnaire were administered, retrieved and analysed. The data were collected and analysis utilizing mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The decision for research questions was based on a criterion level of 2.50, considering mean responses of 2.50 and above as "Agree" and responses below 2.50 as "Disagree. T-test was employed to test the five null hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. Any null hypothesis whose p-value is less than 0.05 will be rejected but otherwise accepted. "Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was employed for the analysis.

Research Question One

Is YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores of respondents on YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Item Statement	Male		Female		Decision
		(n ₁ = 23)		(n ₂ = 16)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	
1	Ability to create professional sale profile on YouTube to increase sales of products and services.	3.26	0.92	2.94	1.12	Agree
2	Ability to create videos that showcase the sale of products and services.	3.00	1.04	3.19	0.83	Agree
3	Ability to create videos to targeted audience to increase sales of products and services.	3.04	0.98	3.25	1.00	Agree
4	Ability to encourage and grow subscriptions to increase sales of products and services.	3.22	1.09	3.13	1.15	Agree
5	Ability to encourage shares to increase sales of products and services.	3.04	0.98	3.00	1.10	Agree
6	Ability to encourage likes to increase sales on products and services.	3.00	1.09	3.38	1.09	Agree
7	Ability to do affiliate marketing to increase sales of products and services.	3.00	1.09	3.19	0.98	Agree
8	Ability to promote products and services to increase sales from time to time.	3.30	0.88	3.06	1.18	Agree
9	Ability to do keyword research to rank products and services.	2.96	1.07	3.25	0.93	Agree
10	Ability to choose contents segments to increase sales of products and services.	3.26	1.01	3.56	0.89	Agree
Grand Mean		3.11	1.02	3.20	1.03	

Key: X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 1 presents the findings on the necessity of YouTube for marketing education graduates as perceived by male and female business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State. The mean values for all ten items ranged from 2.94 to 3.35, all surpassing the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating strong agreement on YouTube's importance. The overall grand mean scores of 3.11 and 3.20 further support this consensus. Additionally, the standard deviations for individual items ranged from 0.83 to 1.18, with overall standard deviations of 1.02 and 1.03, showing that the responses were consistent and closely clustered around the mean. These findings highlight a clear recognition of YouTube as a critical platform for marketing education graduates in the sales of products and services.

Research Question Two

Is WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of respondents on WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Item Statement	Male		Female		Decision
		(n ₁ = 23)		(n ₂ = 16)		
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	
11	Ability to create professional sale profile on WhatsApp to increase sales of products and services.	3.30	0.97	3.13	1.09	Agree
12	Ability to navigate WhatsApp platform to increase sales of products and services.	3.13	1.01	3.44	0.89	Agree
13	Ability to create WhatsApp broadcast to increase sales of products and services.	3.26	1.05	3.06	0.93	Agree
14	Ability to share different products and services with links to increase sales of products and services.	3.09	1.00	3.19	0.91	Agree
15	Ability to use WhatsApp business to increase sales of products and services.	2.87	1.14	3.25	1.18	Agree
16	Ability to chat with clients/prospective clients to increase sales of products and services.	3.04	1.02	3.06	1.06	Agree
17	Ability to promote products and services on WhatsApp status to increase sales.	3.48	0.99	3.06	1.00	Agree
18	Ability to share short videos on WhatsApp status to increase sales of products and services.	3.17	1.11	3.31	1.09	Agree
19	Ability to create channels to increase sales of products and services.	3.17	0.98	3.31	0.87	Agree
20	Ability to create group to increase sales of products and services.	3.22	1.09	3.25	0.77	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.17	1.04	3.21	0.98	

Key: X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 2 shows the findings on the necessity of WhatsApp for marketing education graduates as perceived by male and female business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State. The mean values for all ten items ranged from 2.87 to 3.48, all above the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating

strong agreement on WhatsApp's importance. The overall grand mean scores of 3.17 and 3.21 further support this consensus. Additionally, the standard deviations for individual items ranged from 0.77 to 1.18, with overall standard deviations of 1.04 and 0.98, demonstrating that the responses were consistent and closely clustered around the mean. These findings highlight a clear recognition of WhatsApp as a critical platform for marketing education graduates in the sales of products and services.

Research Question Three

Is Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation scores of respondents on Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State

S/N	Item Statement	Male (n ₁ = 23)		Female (n ₂ = 16)		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	\bar{X}_2	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	
21	Ability to create professional sale profile on Facebook to increase sales of products and services.	3.43	0.84	3.13	1.09	Agree
22	Ability to use Facebook reels to add videos on products and services to increase sales.	3.17	0.98	3.00	1.10	Agree
23	Ability to setup Facebook community to increase sales of products and services.	3.09	1.04	3.19	0.98	Agree
24	Ability to build clients/customers audiences to increase sales of products and services.	3.00	1.00	3.31	1.08	Agree
25	Ability to select and upload products and services on Facebook to increase sales.	3.13	0.92	3.06	1.12	Agree
26	Ability to copy links of products and services on profile wall to increase sales.	3.35	0.98	3.31	0.95	Agree
27	Ability to create ads on Facebook news feed to increase sales of products and service.	3.22	1.00	3.31	0.95	Agree
28	Ability to run ads on Facebook news feed to increase sales of products and services.	3.52	0.85	3.44	0.89	Agree
29	Ability to use Facebook paid method to increase sales of products and services.	3.22	1.00	3.06	1.06	Agree
30	Ability to increase Facebook followers/friends to increase sales of products and services.	3.09	0.95	3.31	0.87	Agree
Grand Mean		3.22	0.96	3.21	1.01	

Key: X = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 3 presents the mean responses of male and female business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State regarding the necessity of the Facebook platform for marketing education graduates in the sales of products and services. The table shows that the mean values for all ten items ranged from 3.00 to 3.52, all above the cut-off point of 2.50. Overall, the grand mean scores of 3.22 and 3.21 were also above the cut-off point, indicating that male and female business

educators agree on the importance of Facebook platform. The standard deviations for individual items ranged from 0.84 to 1.12, with overall standard deviations of 0.96 and 1.01, demonstrating that the responses were consistent and closely clustered around the mean. These findings highlight a clear recognition of Facebook as a critical platform for marketing education graduates in the sales of products and services

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of respondents on in YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Alpha level	Decision
Male	23	3.11	0.98	37	-0.26	0.79	0.05	N/S
Female	16	3.19	0.98					p> 0.05

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Key: \bar{X} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Df = Degree of freedom, Not Significant, p> 0.05

Table 4 presents the results of an independent t-test analysis conducted to assess the disparity in the perceived mean ratings between male and female business educators regarding the YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services in higher institutions in Bayelsa State. Male business educators have a mean of 3.11 with a standard deviation of 0.98, while female business educators have a mean of 3.19 with a standard deviation of 0.98.

The table shows a t-value of -0.26 at 37 degrees of freedom with a p-value of 0.79. Testing at the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted since the p-value (0.79) is greater than 0.05. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators regarding the YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Table 5: t-test Analysis of respondents on in WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Alpha level	Decision
Male	23	3.17	1.00	37	-0.10	0.92	0.05	N/S
Female	16	3.20	0.93					p> 0.05
39								

Key: \bar{X} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Df = Degree of freedom, Not Significant, p> 0.05

Table 5 presents the results of an independent t-test analysis conducted to assess the differences in the perceived mean ratings between male and female business educators regarding the WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services in higher institutions in Bayelsa State. Male business educators have a mean of 3.17 with a standard deviation of 1.00, while female business educators have a mean of 3.20 with a standard deviation of 0.93.

The table shows a t-value of -0.10 at 37 degrees of freedom with a p-value of 0.92. Testing at the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted since the p-value (0.92) is greater than 0.05. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators regarding the WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Hypothesis three

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female business educators on Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of respondents on in Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services as perceived by business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Group	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	T	P-value	Alpha level	Decision
Male	23	3.22	0.92	37	0.30	0.98	0.05	N/S
Female	16	3.21	0.98					p> 0.05
39								

Key: \bar{X} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Df = Degree of freedom, Not Significant, p> 0.05

Table 6 summarizes the results of an independent t-test analysis that evaluated the differences in perceived mean ratings between male and female business educators regarding the Facebook platform needed for marketing education graduates to sell products and services in higher

institutions in Bayelsa State. Male business educators reported a mean of 3.22 with a standard deviation of 0.92, while female business educators reported a mean of 3.21 with a standard deviation of 0.98.

The analysis yielded a t-value of 0.30 at 37 degrees of freedom with a p-value of 0.98. At the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis is accepted since the p-value (0.98) exceeds 0.05. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators regarding the Facebook platform needed for marketing education graduates to sell products and services in higher institutions in Bayelsa State.

Discussion

The finding of the study showed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators regarding YouTube platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services. This implies that differences did not exist in research on YouTube platform required for sales of products and services. The results concurred with the findings of Yusuf (2023) who found that YouTube plays a crucial role in the expansion of businesses because it offers a valuable platform for companies to promote their products and services, engage with customers, and expand their market reach. The results are also in line with the opinion of Rich (2018) who found out that YouTube enables businesses to provide goods or services, market their products, discover new offerings, and improve existing ones through promotional activities.

The finding of the study also showed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators regarding WhatsApp platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services. This also implies that differences did not exist in research on WhatsApp platform required for sales of products and services. This finding is in agreement with Lin (2020) who found that WhatsApp advertising has emerged as a prominent trend among social media platforms, with WhatsApp status, private messages, broadcast messages, and WhatsApp chat groups being inundated with images and videos showcasing various products and services

In addition, the finding of the study revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators regarding Facebook platform required for marketing education graduates for sales of products and services. This equally implies that differences did not exist in research on Facebook platform required for sales of products and services. The results concur with the findings of Arteaga, Cortijo and Javed (2014), who found out that adoption of Facebook has positive effects for the purposes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the role of social media in the modern marketing landscape is indispensable, making it crucial for marketing education graduates to be proficient in utilizing various platforms to effectively promote and sell products and services. This study has underscored the importance of

understanding the perceptions of business educators in tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State regarding essential social media platforms for marketing graduates.

Business educators, with their insights and experience, play a pivotal role in shaping curricula that align with industry needs and trends. Platforms such as YouTube, WhatsApp and Facebook platform each offer unique advantages for marketing, ranging from visual content sharing to professional networking and real-time communication as it is done across the world in this 21st century. By identifying the platforms deemed most critical by educators, this study provides valuable guidance for curriculum development, ensuring that marketing programs remain relevant and effective in preparing graduates for the dynamic digital marketplace.

Recommendation

Based on the perceptions of business educators in higher institutions in Bayelsa State, the following recommendations can be made regarding the use of social media platforms for marketing education graduates:

1. Government should enhance internet connectivity and ensure affordable access to digital tools across Bayelsa State to support seamless social media use.
2. Policy makers should mandate the inclusion of social media marketing and digital literacy in tertiary education curricula to equip students with necessary skills.
3. Educational institutions should develop comprehensive courses that cover various aspects of social media marketing, including content creation, analytics, and platform-specific strategies.
4. Business educators should engage in ongoing professional development to stay abreast of new social media platforms and marketing strategies.
5. Students and marketing education graduates should take the initiative in learning and mastering popular social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, WhatsApp, and emerging platforms like TikTok.

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